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'The Hammer of God' by Arthur C. Clarke as an Eschatological Reading

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ABSTRACT

As human curiosity commenced from the Garden of Eden, it would never stop because every human being is a child of Adam and Eve. By now, this curiosity has come up to the level of exploring other planets. Even the end of this world and its' living being is doubted now. This concept is called 'Eschatology'; a part of theology, and talks about the end of the world or the final fate of humankind. Every religion has peeped into Eschatology. In Christianity, the Bible reveals about the End Time. Many literature corpora have been written about the end of this world. Arthur C. Clarke as a Science Fiction writer has begotten seminal trajectories to the literature world. His Science Fiction depicts future events filled with imagination to inspire readers and accompany them where they have never been before. The Hammer of God by Arthur C. Clarke reveals the technological, physical, and intellectual advancements by 2190 (22nd century world). It unfolds the story of an asteroid called 'Kali' which can destroy entire Earth and how the crew deflects it using technology with the help of an invisible hand. Wilkinson has denoted that 'History was pregnant with the future' (1). This statement can be proved because the Biblical representations are juxtaposed with the Science Fiction 'The Hammer of God'. This research paper streamlines the chain of biblical prophecies with the human accomplishments, and pathetic situations which can be seen in the 22nd century. This article is a content analysis and primary data was collected from the printed book. Collected data then were analyzed qualitatively with respect to the Eschatological representation of the Science Fiction 'The Hammer of God'.

Keywords

Eschatology, Christianity, Science Fiction, asteroid, Biblical prophecy

Introduction

As Douglas and Hillyer explains the term 'Eschatology', it derived from a Greek term 'Eschatos' which indicates 'last' or 'doctrine of last things' (2). Under the concept of Eschatology, two major parts can be observed as Individual Eschatology; what would happen to a person after death, Corporate Eschatology; what would happen to the entire humankind and world, and God's decision of all. This article concerns about the Corporate Eschatology because 'The Hammer of God' unwraps the story of an asteroid which comes towards Earth and collapses everything in a fraction of second. Human beings are always curious about the end of this world and they take actions based on the scope of 'Eschatology'. On one hand, churches have been searching for spiritual facets such as End time, New Heaven, and New Earth; on the other hand, Science and technology has been searching for physical facets such as space and other planets of this universe. According to Menn J, person's view of eschatology influences the way they acts. Of course, other theological, secular, political, economic, relational, and personal factors motivate people to act in different ways (3). Meanwhile, literature is influenced by the concepts of theology, especially Science Fiction by Eschatology. Science Fiction is revealed as a quiddity of both eschatological and technological conceptions. 'The Hammer of God' represents the modern millennium technological developments, with concepts, and characters based on the apocalyptic facets.

The end time is described by some sects of Christianity as a period of tribulation awaiting Christ's second coming.

"These will go away into eternal punishment, but the righteous into eternal life" (4).

As revealed by previous instance, unbelievers would be headed to the punishments while believers would be ushered into their respective eternal destinies at the End of this world. On the other hand, science has observed the end of the world and humankind. Due cause of these incidents and timeframe as follows; within 0-100 million years by volcanic apocalypse, within 450 million years by asteroid threat, within 3 to 4 billion years the core freeze over as Mars, 500,000 years by gamma-ray burst, within the next million years by wandering stars, and between 1 to 7.5 billion years by expanding the sun, our Earth can be ended up. The Hammer of God talks about the year 2109, and the discovery of an asteroid that would collide with Earth and the mission for deflection of asteroid using fuel and nuclear technology. 22nd century stands for 200 million which science believes that Earth would collide with an asteroid. From the title, Arthur C. Clarke streamlines Biblical revealed 'Eschatology' and how they are connected with the novel 'The Hammer of God'.

Literature review

Arthur C. Clarke (1917–2008) was one of the most influential advocates in the twentieth century for the exploration and colonization of space. Science fiction provides readers a platform to go over orbit, galaxies, other planets and travel through space and time, even though they have never been to the neighbor country. The sheer pervasiveness and consumption of Science Fiction today is ground for asserting that our technological imagination is influenced more by Science Fiction media than political or social engagements with technology and the future (5). The vital part of Arthur C. Clarke's writing is indeed, many of the concepts Clarke proposed in his science fiction have continued to inform real-world propositions regarding space travel and extraterrestrial colonization (6). In his article Reid noted that Clarke has given a vivid idea to write this novel as, to educate public people about the asteroids that can hit the Earth meanwhile it could cause to end up lives of millions of people and it may convert the entire climate of the planet (7). As mentioned these lines, all the events set in the past happened at the times and places stated; all those set in the future as possible.

De Vos explained that she believes in the power of storytelling. She thinks it is most fascinating that he loves down there but also for up there, and it is really unusual duality (8). He was able to tell stories both these paces and create interest excitement around both these spaces which is not common. This statement indicates that how wide his imagination is, not only imagination, but also practical involvement in to those areas. On the surface Clarke's oeuvre offers a classic astrofuturist model of progress as technology-driven, but on closer examination it also incorporates a more pessimistic, historically based strand of philosophy, British rather than American (9). Once he had an interview with 'wired.com' and when they asked, as communication using satellite, what could be the next thing to change everything? He replied as 'the brainman' which he has written about in *The Hammer of God*. He took that idea half seriously (10). Even though man, still tries to find out whether they can breathe on moon, Clarke has dreamed to live peacefully on it as civilized people. Not only contemporary people have hope about the lunar civilization, immortal Clarke is on alert about the future of earth, although he is in the heaven. The themes of audience participation and human destiny in outer space are examined in a close reading of these two case studies, and further engagement with cultures of outer space in geography is encouraged (11).

Christian Eschatology

Eschatology stands for the End of this world including every existing living being. Active Christianity declared that time of peace and harmony on Earth where the justice of Jesus and saints will reign is called 'Millennium'. All wrongs are set right and the world would be cleaned of all evils by the time. Isaiah 65:20-25 provides a complete summary of the wonder and peace of period. The novel *The Hammer of God* is at the edge of millennium age, in particular there are lot of evidences can be found related to the time of thousand

years that Bible mentioned both related to God's wrath and Satan's abundance. Simple meaning of the millennium is thousand years believing all the sins will be banished and world will be peaceful.

“But the day of the Lord will come as a thief in the night, in which the heavens will pass away with a great noise, and the elements will melt with fervent heat; both the earth and the works that are in it will be burned up” (12).

When God arrive, believers will be accompanied to the heaven and sinners will be burnt up. The day, the lord arrives, like a robber, just as a thief appears suddenly, causing great tragedy and panic. Unexpectedly and without warning, the day of the lord would come. This will cause great distress and catastrophic calamity of nations. It is obviously getting connected with the novel ‘*The Hammer of God*’?

This novel consists with four encounters as; Oregon 1972, Tunguska 1908, Gulf of Mexico 65,000,000 BP (before preset), and encounter four. These encounters elucidate that how earth has been faced to destroy by asteroid and other disasters, and how this globe and civilization would be occurred throughout this universe during 22nd century. Blake Dodge by NASA, on 24th of August 2020, mentioned that a fridge-size asteroid is headed towards earth has a slim chance to enter in to earth's atmosphere on 2nd of November, and it is tend to burn up anyway before reaching the ground (13). What are these asteroids? Are they signs of God? It is needed to notice that Clarke has mentioned that ‘sooner or later, we will meet Kali’. Eschatology now has come up with more practical pace since humankind seeks for water on Mars to solve the problems of the planet Earth. Even though people achieve technical advancements, on the other hand their sustainability is still and stupendous. ‘Everyone knew that Earth was noisy, smelly, polluted, and horribly overcrowded’ almost three billion people! Not to mention with its hurricanes, earthquakes, volcanoes.’ (14). If people act not as humans with humility, advanced brain, could anyone guarantees that nature and the ruler, the invisible hand will not take an action?

Bible mentions about End time and people who, would be peaceful, have advanced mindset and are still believe in Satan's advices. Clarke represents particular human qualities in the novel providing specimens from advanced technological, intellectual, physical, and moral developments in 22nd century inspired from the Bible.

Technological developments

Bible prophecies unfold the lifestyle of the End Time as this:

“They will build houses and dwell in them; they will plant vineyards and eat their fruit. No longer will they build houses and others live in them, or plant and others eat. For as the days of a tree, so will be the days of my people; my chosen ones will long enjoy the works of their hands. They will not toil in vain or bear children doomed to misfortune; says the LORD (15).

Technologies have been changing over time, but the concepts and ideas that Bible owns would become a reality. Due to the advancement of thinking patterns of people, these prophecies have been become true. Clarke has utilized his knowledge and experience with his future dreams of peaceful world, but he blended his thoughts with the prophecies of Bible. As above Bible quote reveals, future houses would be well developed with human achievements, people would build houses and even grow plants in their houses. They would enjoy works of their hands; which they have invented and developed from their knowledge. In 22nd century, on the view of Clarke, technology would be advanced as follows;

- a. House central- It is a machine, a brain like a robot which is built inputting all the information about the earth. People can ask any question about anything that they do not know, but House Central knows everything. Even they can send a photo to take information. This indicates people would make machines which can exceed the memory of a human being and utilize them to comfort their lives.
- b. Skylift Service- It is a system that sets the houses down in everywhere. By the time there are no deserts, because all part of the earth is filled with people. In this novel Skylift service sets the house down in Africa with fully furnished and secure.
- c. Food recycling system- People can recycle the food they take, and it can be taken as a worth solution to food wastage of contemporary society. People have small gardens in their home which is opened to sunlight growing flowers and other plants as previous biblical quote mentioned it.
- d. Home technology- This concept is taken from 'fuller house' which has been suggested by Buckminster Fuller, American architect, system theorist, author, designer, inventor and futurist. His concept of 'Dymaxion house' inspired Clarke to write about the house which protagonist and his family share. It is too small cottage rather than a house that people can rent, but most rooms are multifunctional and could be transformed by commands, furniture can metamorphose, ceiling and walls can be vanished or replaced.
- e. Artificial meat- Eating natural meat hacked from dead animal would have been stopped by the time 2190.

“The wolf and the lamb will feed together, and the lion will eat straw like the ox, but dust will be the serpent’s food. They will neither harm nor destroy on all my holy mountain.” (16)

- f. Superoxide enzymes- It wins the Nobel Prize for medicine that developed DNA to extend life of wo(man) at least fifty years and treatments are inexpensive. Shonebarger explained that a person’s birth in the Millennium Age will live to be hundreds of years old, like the extended life spans typical in the Pre-Flood Age (17) By the Millennium age people will live longer over centuries and Clarke elucidates that the humankind’s lives over 100 years.
- g. Religions arise by the time 2190- As mentioned in Revelation

“There is a white horse. He who sat on it had a bow; and a crown was given to him, and he went out conquering and to conquer” (18).

Not only one horse in the New Testament, there are four horses as white horse, red horse, black horse, and pale/green horse. Dan has clearly stated that according to Zech 6:5, spirits of the world are represented by the four horses. Catholicism, Communism, Capitalism, and Islam are most likely represented by these four horses and horsemen. Furthermore, due to the Christian Pope wears white and he has been crowned while Catholic Church brings peace upon the humankind this white horses would be Christianity. On the other hand, green horse would be Islamic religion, because they try to take power by involving into the War, hunger, and crime while the red horse is represented by communist countries both USSR and China as the horse who had a great sword of military power. Moreover the money, free trade, even try to bill even to wheat by Penny? It is Capitalism which mainly centered into Northern part of the world (19)

In the novel, Clarke has introduced a religion called ‘Chrislam’ that is spread by a Prophet Fathima Magdelene, and developed by electronic facilities based on byte. Here it is needed to mention that this prophet was Ruby Goldenberg before ten years, who belongs to Rabbi father (a person appointed as a Jewish religious leader), who studied her degree in Islamic college but only completed two semesters, who expelled from it and begot a child without legal father, who act as bisexual person and appeared after ten years as a prophet.

“For there shall arise false Christs, and false prophets, and shall show great signs and wonders; in so much that, if it were possible, they shall deceive the very elect.”

As time lapses First she makes a connection with an extreme wealthy person who has connections in Virtual Reality technology and 50 they convert three Testaments of Latter-Day Koran into electronic form. But when it comes to the 4th version, they want to use it by individual user and when any other user tries, it would definitely harm the entire mental system of that person? What it is insisted? The freedom of that religion is to be questioned? Dan has illuminated that —The Antichrist and the False Prophet will execute anyone who does not submit to their world religion. - Rev 13:15 (20). But this religion cannot overcome other religions. As Dan explained that is directly connected into above damages that would happen if someone tries to change it and it have not been lived long life as main religions.

Second wave is called as —The Reborn another gang that leads by Al Haj, who is the son of Fathima Magledene and this group collaborates to escape from Kali, the asteroid. They have made a wide dish on the far side of the Moon to rescue people and join to Reborn group by doing some installments, not only that they could give eternal life for the members. “Indeed, many thought it would be best for the human race to remain silent”. Even if lot of religion (51) is available people do not criticize and it is crystal clear that every religion survives until problem arises within their group or any logical dilemma comes to break up their motifs.

Conclusion

The novel *The Hammer of God* focuses on the End Time, the technological, physical, moral, religious, and spiritual changes that will have been driven by the time 2190. The biblical prophecies about End time and different facets that Clarke has streamlined in this novel are interconnected. From 15th century, (with the earliest Science Fiction in the history is ‘The Chemical Wedding’ (1616) by Johann Valentin Andreae (21), discusses about a man who participates in mysterious royal wedding Science Fiction has been connected with theological, mythological, and futuristic imaginations which reader can enhance their curiosity about this world.

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